

MAGNETIC CONSTRAINTS ON THE SPACE WEATHERING STATE OF THE CHANG'E-5 SOILS.

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Introduction: Space weathering is a primary process altering the lunar surface, producing submicroscopic iron particles embedded in soil grains, which have diagnostic magnetic and spectroscopic effects [1]. However, the space weathering of lunar soils from young geological units, such as the Chang'e-5 (CE-5) landing site (~2.0 Ga) [2, 3], remains mysterious without solid constraints from returned samples. The CE-5 mission has provided an unprecedented opportunity to reveal geologically recent space weathering characteristics with both returned soil samples and in situ data.

Method: Magnetic approaches, which have been widely used to quantify the maturity state of lunar soils since the Apollo era [4], were applied to characterize the CE-5 lunar soils for the first time. CE-5 soil samples CE5C0600 (from surface), CE5Z0906YJ (from a depth of 0.10 m), CE5Z0204YJ (from a depth of 0.65 m), and basaltic fragments selected from them were used for magnetic measurements.

Vibrating Sample Magnetometer (VSM): The hysteresis parameters of the CE-5 lunar soil CE5C0600, and lithic fragments selected from soils CE5C0600 (CE5-0600-01), CE5Z0906YJ (CE5-0906-01), and CE5Z0204YJ (CE5-0204-01), were obtained by the Lake Shore 8604 VSM. The hysteresis loop was measured at room temperature with a maximum field of 1.9 T. Saturation magnetization (M_s), saturation remanent magnetization (M_{rs}), and coercivity (H_c) were calculated with HystLab, and remanent coercivity (H_{cr}) as estimated by the Delta M curve obtained by HYSITS. The Day plot was produced according to M_{rs}/M_s and H_{cr}/H_c to evaluate the relative domain state of kamacite-bearing materials [5].

The weight percentage of Fe^0 in the CE-5 lunar soil and lithic fragments was calculated by dividing their M_s values by that of pure metallic iron (218 Am²/kg) and multiplying by 100. The Fe^0 weight abundance of Apollo samples [6] was calculated in the same way.

Diagrams of the first-order reversal curves (FORC) provide much more abundant information about magnetic assemblages than standard hysteresis measurements, including switching fields and local interaction fields. FORCs of the CE5C0600 were measured by VSM with a saturation field of 0.9 T. The FORC curves were then processed by FORCinel v3.08 to derive the FORC diagram.

Electron Paramagnetic Resonance Spectrometer (EPR): The ferromagnetic resonance (FMR) spectra of the CE-5 lunar soil CE5C0600 and 16 selected

lithic fragments were obtained by the Bruker A300-8/2.7 EPR Spectrometer. The FMR spectra were measured at room temperature operating at a nominal frequency of 9.9 GHz with a sweep width of 10,000 G. A (amplitude) and ΔH (linewidth) values were measured from each obtained FMR spectra.

Typically, I_s/FeO (the intensity of the characteristic ferromagnetic resonance normalized to total iron content, where $I_s = (\Delta H)^2 \cdot A/m$, m represents mass) was calculated directly from the EPR data of Apollo/Luna samples [4]. However, since the amplitude is recorded in arbitrary units that need to be calibrated by samples with known I_s/FeO values, it is not possible for this study to compute

them directly from the EPR data; therefore, the FMR spectra were only used for relative comparison, after normalizing the A value of each spectrum to the A value of CE5-0906-02 (A_{Norm}).

Fig 1. VSM Day plot, EPR spectra, and Mössbauer spectrum of Chang'e-5 lunar soils and selected basaltic fragments.

Mössbauer Spectrometer: The ⁵⁷Fe Mössbauer spectrum of 21.15 mg CE5C0600 was recorded by a WSS-10 Mössbauer Spectrometer. The spectrum was measured in transmission mode with a 25 mCi ⁵⁷Co (Rh) source at room temperature for 7 days; the Doppler velocity was calibrated by 25 μm α -Fe. The measured spectrum was then fitted using the Lorentz absorption curve by MossWinn4.0. The relative abundance of Magnetic 1 (Fe^0), Doublet 1 (pyroxene M1 site/olivine Fe^{2+}), Doublet 2 (pyroxene M2 site/glass Fe^{2+}), and Doublet 3 (ilmenite Fe^{2+}) was then quantified by integrating the absorption areas of

each sub-spectrum. The Fe^0 abundance in CE5C0600 was then calculated based on the relative abundance of Fe^0 in all iron species and the bulk FeO content in the soil.

Fig 2. Linear relationship between Fe^0/FeO and Is/FeO index of lunar mare soils.

Conclusions: According to the VSM measurements, the bulk CE5C0600 soil has the highest M_s ($5.54 \times 10^{-6} \text{ Am}^2$), followed by three basaltic fragments CE5-0600-01 ($1.13 \times 10^{-6} \text{ Am}^2$), CE5-0906-01 ($1.00 \times 10^{-6} \text{ Am}^2$), and CE5-0204-01 ($9.10 \times 10^{-7} \text{ Am}^2$). Their M_s values yield Fe^0 abundances of 0.42% (CE5C0600), 0.10% (CE5-0600-01), 0.09% (CE5-0906-01), and 0.08% (CE5-0204-01), respectively.

The Is/FeO value is a widely used maturity index [4] but it is not possible to compute it here based on EPR measurements because of the lack of calibrations. Alternatively, a linear relationship ($y = 5.88 \times 10^{-4} x + 0.0105$) between Fe^0/FeO and Is/FeO of lunar mare soils was derived from the data of [4] (Fig. 2a). Based on this relationship, the Is/FeO value of the bulk soil CE5C0600 was estimated to be $14 \pm 6 / -10$, considering an Fe^0 abundance of 0.42% and an FeO abundance of 22.22% [7]. These values are among the most immature soils on the Moon, agreeing with the agglutinate and Ni contents (Fig. 2bc).

The Day plot of hysteresis parameters summarized by [6] and this study is shown in Fig. 1a. CE5C0600 bulk soil has the highest M_r/M_s and lowest H_{cr}/H_c values compared to the selected clasts, suggesting a relatively fine domain state for the bulk soil compared with the local basalt and Apollo soils. CE-5 basaltic fragments have H_{cr}/H_c values comparable to Apollo basalts, but their

M_r/M_s values are relatively higher. The FORC of CE5C0600 soil has a weak positive peak at around 2 mT and the contours systematically diverge along the H_u axis, forming a triangle distribution, indicating a pseudo-single domain behavior.

As for the EPR measurements (Fig. 1b), CE5C0600 has diagnostic absorptions of Fe^0 with a g factor of ~ 2.1 . It has the largest ΔH value of all returned lunar soils (860 G). The FeO abundance and ΔH value of CE5C0600 are located on the linear trend derived from previously analyzed lunar soils [4], indicating that the ΔH of CE-5 soil is controlled by composition. The A value of the FMR spectra was used to compare their relative spin concentrations, and therefore the relative Fe^0 abundance. The bulk soil CE5C0600 has the largest A value, followed by CE5-0600-02 and CE5-0600-03 with glassy coatings on the grain. Other basaltic fragments in the FMR spectra are relatively homogeneous, as in the hysteresis loops.

In addition, Mössbauer spectra of CE-5 soil CE5C0600 were obtained (Fig. 1c) and have clear absorptions of pyroxene M1 site/olivine Fe^{2+} (33.4%) and M2 site/glass Fe^{2+} (55.5%), as well as ilmenite Fe^{2+} site (9.1%). The absorption of Fe^0 is weak, with a relative abundance of 2.5%, corresponding to an absolute abundance of 0.43% in the bulk soil. This value matches well with the abundance of the bulk soil (0.42%) measured by VSM.

Discussion: We propose that the immature nature of the CE-5 soils is the result of the young age of the CE-5 landing mare unit (located on one of the youngest lunar mare units [8]) and the plume-regolith interactions at the landing site. Several recent studies [9-11] have discussed the maturity of the CE-5 soil but they do not yet reach a consensus on whether the CE-5 soil is mature or immature. Based on our current analysis of CE-5 soils, we suggest continuing to use the Is/FeO index as the main diagnostic criterion to distinguish the maturity state of lunar soil. The lack of calibration targets in directly measuring Is/FeO values emphasizes the importance of cooperation internationally between spacefaring countries in analyzing space materials.

References: [1] Pieters C. M., and Noble S. K. (2016) *JGR-P*, 121, 1865-1884. [2] Li Q. et al. (2021) *Nature*, 600, 54-58. [3] Che X. et al. (2021) *Science*, 374, 887-890. [4] Richard R. V. (1978) *9th LPSC*, 2287-2297. [5] Dunlop D. J. (2002) *JGR*, 107(B3), 2056. [6] Strauss B. E. et al. (2021) *JGR-P*, 126, e2020JE006715. [7] Zong K. et al. (2022) *GCA*, 335, 284-296. [8] Qian Y. et al. (2023) *NA*, 7, 287-297. [9] Li C. et al. (2022) *NSR*, 9, nwab188. [10] Wu X. et al (2022) *EPSL*, 594, 117747. [11] Lu X. et al. (2023) *NA*, 7, 142-151.